

ROLE OF FUNCTIONAL BREAD IN NUTRITION OF YOUNG CHILDREN

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Abstract: During childhood it is vital to take care of the diet to guarantee good development and growth. At this stage it is also important to transmit healthy habits, such as eating habits, so that the little ones can adapt and maintain them throughout their lives.

Key words: nutrition, young children, fat, kindergarten, Protein, vitamin, bread, nutrients.

INTRODUCTION

It is known to everyone that studying the rational nutrition of different population groups has become one of the urgent problems of today. It is talked about in many places. Even now, a lot of work is being done on this problem in a number of countries and in our Republic. But the solution to this problem is delayed due to several reasons. For example, it was found that the problem of eating also occurs in kindergarten children.

The baby's body begins to adapt to the addition of fats to its food from the age of three weeks. These fats can be in the form of: fish oil, vegetable oil, milk fat, etc. Studies conducted on the study of fat metabolism in the body of one-year-old children show that fats rich in unsaturated fatty acids (fish oil, vegetable oils) in their body are better compared to cow's milk fat. will be done. Accordingly, it is appropriate to pay more attention to the use of oils rich in unsaturated fatty acids in children's diets. But it is also important that the amount of vegetable (or fish) oil in the daily diet of young children should not exceed 10% of total fats. The introduction of cottage cheese and oils into children's food should be done gradually.

The organization of children's nutrition in kindergartens, that is, providing their body with necessary nutrients and vitamins in terms of quantity and quality in accordance with the requirements of the growing body, is of great importance for their normal growth and development. The composition of food should be varied, well prepared and rich in all substances necessary for the child's body. It is also required that the diet is properly structured.

The organization of children's meals should be carried out by qualified specialist nurses. Attention is paid to the following:

1. Quality of food products brought to kindergarten. Their storage conditions and period of realization.
2. Creating menus. Physiological value of food.
3. Proper use of food products in cooking.
4. Correctness of cooking technology.
5. The quality of the prepared food, it should be given correctly according to the age of the children.
6. Analysis of the composition of food for different age groups (by the method of calculation based on tables).
7. Daily monitoring of their use according to the list of approved products.
8. Compilation of relevant documents on nutrition ("Amount of animal protein in children's diet by age groups", "Analysis of the chemical composition of food", "Vitaminization of food" and other magazines).
9. Consideration of relevant issues in the catering board of the institution.
10. Working with parents on the proper organization of meals at home.

Kindergarten teachers should be familiar with the basics of healthy children's nutrition and have the skills to monitor their nutrition.

It is known that many shortcomings are allowed in the organization of children's meals in kindergartens. It was found that one of the most common mistakes is the low amount of animal proteins and irreplaceable amino acids in the diet. The main reason for this is the wrong choice of products for the menu and ignorance of their composition. It is often found that the price of food products

does not correspond to their biological value. For example, cheap but high biological value products (liver, kidney, cottage cheese, beans, peas, wheat groats, etc.) are rarely used in food rations. Oils are used incorrectly in most cases, the used vegetable oils are hardly consumed in their natural form, their diversity is not paid attention to (in most cases, only cottonseed oil is used). Fruits, vegetables and dairy products are rare in the rations. As a result of this, irreplaceable amino acids, unsaturated fatty acids, minerals, microelements and natural vitamins decrease in food.

Although how you eat bread and how you enjoy it affects how healthy it is, bread offers a variety of health benefits. These nutritional aspects can make bread an important part of your diet. Thus, enjoying bread can become part of a balanced diet. Then you can get various health benefits of bread, such as:

Getting enough protein in your diet can help:

- : Protein reduces levels of Ghrelin, the hunger hormone. This will help you feel fuller while eating less and avoid overeating.
- Protein is essential for building and maintaining muscle mass and strength. If you want to lose weight without losing muscle, eat enough protein.
- protein intake helps maintain bone mass with age. This prevents cracks and other problems.

Bread, in addition to other protein-rich foods, can give you those and other benefits of protein. As a source of protein, bread is often suitable for vegans and vegetarians. If you don't eat meat, you may have a problem getting protein in your diet. Eating bread and other protein alternatives can help you reach your daily protein goal.

The nutritional value of bread already contains some important nutrients. But bakeries can enrich their products with additional micronutrients, making bread more beneficial for health.

- Iron: this trace mineral helps create certain hormones and brings oxygen to our muscles.

- Thiamine: Thiamine, also known as vitamin B1, helps our bodies convert nutrients into energy.
- Riboflavin: Also known as vitamin B2, riboflavin helps with cell function, fat metabolism, and energy production.
- Niacin: Also known as vitamin B3, niacin helps our body get energy from food.
- Calcium: This micromineral supports our bones and teeth. It also helps blood vessels to contract and muscles to work.

DISCUSSION

Another mistake made in the organization of meals in kindergartens is the absence of a differential approach to food preparation according to age groups. The amount of products in the food of young and old children should not be allowed to be the same. Such a situation leads to the fact that food does not correspond to the physiological demand for nutrients in children of different ages. As a result, young children receive more nutrients, such as proteins, according to their physiological requirements, while older children receive less.

Eating disorders are uncontrolled eating. If different age groups are not taken into account when calculating the amount of products used for food preparation, it will not be possible to calculate the chemical composition of rations for a separate time period. As a result, it is impossible to know to what extent children's nutritional needs are being met.

The quality of children's nutrition depends on many factors: the correct use of products in food preparation, compliance with the rules of culinary processing, correct implementation of portion distribution. It is of great importance that children know the rules of organizing the proper nutrition of kitchen workers, the quality and composition of food.

So, it can be said that neglect is the primary cause of kindergarten children's malnutrition. Establishing proper nutrition of kindergarten children is primarily the work of parents and kindergarten teachers. Negligence of any of them can have serious consequences. The role of kindergarten teachers is especially important in this regard. It was found that kindergarten children eat 80% of their daily meals in

kindergarten. So, in this process, it is necessary for kindergarten teachers to pay serious attention to their proper and reasonable nutrition. Otherwise, their young body may undergo various negative changes.

THE RESULT

It is important to note that the organism of kindergarten children is a growing organism, and their demand for basic nutrients, vitamins and minerals is somewhat higher. Because their body has a strong metabolism, the process of cell division and reproduction is very fast. Therefore, they have higher nutrient requirements for growth and development than adults. The first thing to pay attention to in the nutrition of kindergarten children is their growth. Children's nutritional needs must be met from a growth standpoint. For example, for 3-7-year-old children, the daily requirement for proteins is 60 g, for fat - 60 g, and for carbohydrates - 240 g. Eating more or less of the above-mentioned nutrients can negatively affect normal growth and development. Excessive or excessive consumption of nutrients on the one hand leads to the transformation of these substances into harmful or even toxic substances, and on the other hand leads to obesity.

In this regard, the role of vitamins is especially important. Most studies show that vitamin deficiency leads to severe growth retardation, mental and physical retardation. At the same time, lack of various vitamins in the diet leads to various unpleasant diseases. It weakens the resistance and immunity of the young organism.

One thing to consider in the diet of kindergarten children is that they often love to eat sweets. As a result, appetite for food may decrease. Or the amount of carbon dioxide in the body may increase due to the increase in sweets in the food. That's why sweets should not exceed the norm in children's food. Honey is the best dessert in this regard. Giving honey instead of sugar is more beneficial for a young body. Because honey contains a lot of bioactive substances, useful trace elements, and vitamins. And these substances are very important for children.

Careful attention should be paid to the availability of sufficient dietary fibers in the food of kindergarten children. It is advisable to give them products rich in dietary fibers (cabbage, carrots, various other vegetables, apples, black bread). Good, healthy development of kindergarten children depends in many ways on dietary fibers.

As children grow older, it is useful to give them hard bread, crackers, and meat bones to develop their chewing muscles.

10 BREAD-BASED BABY RECIPE IDEAS

Grilled, sliced, in a sandwich or in breadcrumbs, bread has more than one asset to seduce Baby and all other eaters!

Country bread (from 12 months)

Panade (from 12 months)

French toast (from 12 months)

Apple slice (from 12 months)

Sailor sandwich (from 12 months)

Sweet pizza (from 12 months)

Breadsticks (from 12 months)

Mint meatballs (from 12 months)

Italian pudding (from 15 months)

Chicken tortilla (from 18 months)

Bread provides calories (energy) primarily in the form of carbohydrates. Carbs are your body's preferred energy source. When you eat bread, you are providing your body with fuel for your daily activities.

If you choose bread made from whole grains, you're also getting a source of fiber. Whole grains high in fiber have been shown to help reduce the risks of cardiovascular disease. Consuming 28 to 30 grams each day of whole grains may lower total serum cholesterol and low-density lipoprotein (LDL), considered “bad” cholesterol.

May Help with Blood Sugar Control

Studies show that consuming more whole grains can help control blood sugar levels and reduce the risk of type 2 diabetes. Research shows eating 1.5 servings of whole grains, such as bread, daily can help lower blood sugar and insulin levels.

May Support Weight Loss

Weight loss experts generally recommend consuming foods with fiber if you're trying to lose weight. Fiber can help you feel more satisfied after eating less, which can be useful if you're trying to create the calorie deficit needed for weight loss.

Research supports consuming whole grains for reaching a healthy weight. Those who consume more whole grains tend to have more ideal body fat percentages and lower weight than those who do not.

CONCLUSION

In general, it depends on their parents and kindergarten teachers to organize and implement a reasonable diet of kindergarten children.

After all, what parents or guardians give to children, what they don't give them, and in what order they give them, have a serious impact on their nutritional status. A child grows and develops depending on what he eats. Therefore, first of all, parents should worry about this. Also, it will be good to conduct educational activities among kindergarten teachers about the importance of healthy eating and its organization.

Leftover Bread is a source of vitamins. It provides water-soluble vitamins of the b group, namely vitamin B1 or thiamin, vitamin B2 or riboflavin, vitamin B3 or niacin, vitamin B6 or pyridoxine, and vitamin B9 or folic acid.

In addition, it contains numerous minerals such as phosphorus, magnesium, calcium and potassium necessary for our body to correctly develop various fundamental functions. For example, calcium is responsible for the formation of bones and teeth, as well as blood clotting and nerve transmission; the phosphorus to the like calcium, bones and teeth and maintains the acid-base

balance; the magnesium plays an important role in the production and transport of energy; and potassium (in which whole wheat bread is especially rich), controls the heart rate, intervenes in the generation of nerve impulses and in muscle contraction.

Wheat is a product very rich in resistant starch and fiber, but this is concentrated in the bran, which is eliminated to obtain white flour and the subsequent production of white bread (the most consumed in developed countries). However, in recent years there has been an increase in the consumption of whole wheat bread, which plays a very important role in the contribution of dietary fiber in amounts between 2 and 6 times higher than those of white bread.

Several decades ago scientists and researchers discovered the relationship between fiber consumption through diet and a lower prevalence of diseases such as diabetes and cholesterol, in addition to its intestinal regulatory role. The fiber provided by bread is insoluble, and therefore provides a greater laxative effect, helping to facilitate intestinal transit and reduce its duration.

Bread is a staple food for the little ones. It is advisable for children to eat bread at breakfast, recess and snack, as it helps them to have better school performance.

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